

ТВОРЧЕСКАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ

Абдусаламова Райхона Абдурашид кизи

Термезский государственный педагогический институт

Факультет дошкольного образования

студент 2-го курса

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074361>

Аннотация: в данной статье говорится о важности формирования творческой активности дошкольников в дошкольных образовательных организациях. Познавательный процесс дошкольника развивается в процессе творческой деятельности.

Ключевые слова: дошкольный возраст, ребенок, познание, творчество, деятельность, исследование, творческая деятельность, направленность, планомерность, норма, критерий, среда, предметы, познание, овладение;

Annotation: this article talks about the importance of forming the creative activity of preschoolers in preschool educational organizations. The cognitive process of a preschooler develops in the process of creative activity.

Key words: preschool age, child, cognition, creativity, activity, research, creative activity, orientation, regularity, norm, criterion, environment, objects, cognition, mastery;

Today in our country there are many problems in the development of creative qualities in preschool children, many new laws and decrees are being adopted in our state to solve them. Through creative images in preparatory groups, the school seeks to take into account specific cooperation between the social environment, peers, all representatives of the family in order to develop moral qualities and relate to human interests, as well as to reflect in the life of society. However, as a result of the changing demands of the Times and the worldview of people, problems arise with the provision of moral education in preschool children.

In order to further improve the preschool education system, ensure equal use of quality preschool education of children, to develop the non-governmental sector of preschool services, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan SH.M.In accordance with Mirziyoyev's decision PQ-3955 "on measures to improve the management of the preschool education system" of September 30, 2018:

- Further improvement of the regulatory legal framework in the field of preschool education in accordance with the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030;
- creating conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children;
- improving the management system of preschool education, ensuring transparency and effectiveness of financing the activities of preschool educational organizations;
- introduction of completely new approaches to the preschool education system for the training, retraining, professional development, selection and development of employees of the preschool education system;
- the pedagogical formation of the exact moral behavior of preschool children in the upbringing of children in preschool educational organizations, as well as the formation of moral qualities of family members, especially representatives of the older generation in the family, in the child are becoming an urgent issue today.

In a preschool child, the process of cognition develops in the process of creative activities. In the process of completing the given task, the need for activities aimed at a specific goal, Planned, having norms and criteria, realizing oneself is felt for the manifestation of a child's creative activity. This entails mastering in the child the objects of the environment and knowledge about them; generating educational efficiency, relying on previous types of activity.

In particular, "how to educate the features of creativity in preschool children?"- the actual problem did not arise today. Azal-the issue of the development of creative abilities in a person, which has long been the beginning of creativity, interests both educators and researchers who are directly involved in children's educational education until the present time. Education and upbringing, the formation of personality in society, the development of abilities still remain relevant issues. The problem of developing the technology for the formation of creative activity in preschool children is one of the multifaceted pedagogical - psychological social tasks and is one of the urgent tasks for the social development and development of society.

Creativity-appears in different situations of activity. Curiosity involves the process of inspiration, aspiration, etc., from the appearance of creativity in the human mind in the highest way to its manifestation. The need for creative activity of a person indicates a new, previously unfulfilled desire for creativity in the activity. In children of preschool age, any shoots of creative activity cannot

mature beyond Education, Activity. In the educational process, the emergence of hidden talents in children, the creation of opportunities for their activity from preschool age, the development of creativity in them is considered a pledge of adulthood of competitive personnel who in the future will be able to show high potential, socially active, sharp mentality, the ability to innovate. This corresponds to one of the priorities of our state – the idea of maturing a harmonious person in every possible way. The formation of creative activity in children in preschool education is considered an important component of the educational process. The age and psychological characteristics of children, active and leading subjects of preschool education, as well as the peculiarities of Fine Arts, labor, music and physical education, require a creative approach from the educator.

There are enough psychological reasons to believe that every child contains the potential for creativity. In practice, some limitations must be overcome. First of all, it is impossible to convey, "broadcast" creativity as knowledge or skills. Second, true creativity in any field "creates a strong psychological dominant, covering the whole person." The task is to help the child get in touch with the position of the creator. By nature, children's creativity is synthetic and often improvisational. The synthesis of emotional sensitivity and thinking, logic and intuition, creative imagination and the ability to make quick decisions plays a leading role in musical creativity. The process of children's creativity awakens in children the desire to act sincerely and naturally. In conclusion, I would like to note that when I work in this direction, I am sure that performing creative works by children using various methods and methods, materials, original techniques, creative tasks will allow children to feel unforgettable positive emotions. I got Children are opening up great opportunities to express their fantasies, desires and themselves. In general, children are interested in creative research and solutions, children learn to work with different materials, children develop confidence in their abilities, and their artistic horizons are expanding.

Literature used:

1. M Kuvvatova, F Kholmuminova (2023). Development of creativity of students of higher educational institutions pedagogical justification International Conference On Higher Education Teaching 1 (3), 110-111
2. QM Hikmatullayevna (2022). TO DEVELOP THE CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION IMPORTANCE TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI 2 (12), 262-264

3. M Quvvatova, R Abdusalomova (2023). REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES BASED ON A COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH *Наука и инновация* 1 (9), 137-139
4. Quvvatova, M. H. (2023). TALABALARNING KREATIVLILIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK JIHATLARINI NAZARIY ASOSLASH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 382–386. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3993>
5. Quvvatova, M. H., & Nabiyeva, F. I. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINING KREATIVLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK TIZIMI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 80–82. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3929>
6. Quvvatova, M. H., & Mahmudova, S. S. qizi. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINING KREATIVLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MAZMUNI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 86–88. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3931>
7. Quvvatova, M. H., & Abdusalomova, R. A. qizi. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINING KREATIVLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK JIHATLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 77–79. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3928>
8. Quvvatova, M. H., & Abdusalomova, R. A. qizi. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 208–211. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3729>
9. ST Xabilova, M Nazarova "MENTAL EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN" *Innovative research in modern education* 97-99 2023.5.17 <http://aidlix.com/index.php/ca/article/view/651>
10. S Xabilova "EDUCATION OF FUTURE PRESCHOOL TEACHERS IN A MODERN SPIRIT" *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research* 3(4) 132-135 2023.4.26 <http://www.researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/1234>
11. Xabilova, S. (2023). THE PECULIARITY OF FORMING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL-PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF EDUCATORS. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(6), 202–204. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3373>
12. Xabilova, S. T. qizi, & Nazarova, M. (2023). TARBIYA TURLARI VA ULARNING SHAXS KAMOLOTIGA TA'SIRI. *Educational Research in Universal*

- Sciences, 2(10), 94–96. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3809>
13. Xabilova , S. T. qizi, & Payg'amova , H. (2023). PEDAGOG - TARBIYACHI SHAXSINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 100–102. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3811>
14. Xabilova, S. T. qizi, & Ziyodullayeva , M. (2023). HOZIRGI JAMIYATDA TARBIYACHI SHAXSIGA QO'YILADIGAN TALAB VA VAZIFALAR. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 97–99. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3810>
15. Xabilova, S. T. qizi. (2023). BO'LAJAK TARBIYACHILARNING KASBIY SHAXSIY SIFATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 215–218. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3731>
16. X Nuritdinova “MAKTABGACHA TAYYORLOV YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI MAKTAB TA'LIMIGA TAYYORLASHNING PEDAGOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI” Евразийский журнал академических исследований 2022/3/17 <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/1492>
17. X Nuritdinova “SHAXSNING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING AMALIY VAZIFALARI” Zamonaviy dunyoda pedagogika va psixologiya: Nazariy va amaliy izlanishlar 2022/12/15 <https://zenodo.org/record/7445514>
18. XN Nuritdinova. “KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIKNING MOHIYATI VA UNING MUTAXASSISNI KASBIY SHAKLLANISHIDAGI O'RNI” Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences. 1, № 7, 158-160, 2022.12.15
19. X Nuritdinova. “MULOQOT MUAMMOLARIDA KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIKNING MAZMUN TAVSIFI” «zamonaviy Dunyoda Innovatsion Tadqiqotlar: Nazariya Va Amaliyot» Nomli Ilmiy, Masofaviy, Onlayn Konferensiya, 1(28), 135–137. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7445534>
20. XN Nuritdinova. “TALABALARNING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLILIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH SHART-SHAROITLARI” Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2, № 9, 212-214, 2023.9.21
21. XN Nuritdinova “TA'LIM JARAYONIDA BO 'LAJAK MUTAXASSISLARNING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLILIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI KASBIY TAYYORGARLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH” Экономика и социум, 5-1 (108), 252-255, 2023, <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ta-lim-jarayonida-bo-lajak-mutaxassislarning-kommunikativ-kompetentlilagini-rivojlantirish-orqali-kasbiy-tayyorgarligini>

22. X Нуритдинова “Общетеоретические аспекты определения содержания образования и проектирования педагогической науки” Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education 1, № 6, 151-154 2023.5.17

23. Nuritdinova , X. N., & Bozorova, D. M. qizi. (2023). TALABALARNING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLILIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MAZMUNI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 89–92. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/3932>